

A Comparative Analysis Between Scan-path and Fixations on Event-Related Potentials

Fatima Isiaka

Department of Computer Science, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

Sophia Al Sharji

Department of Computing, Sheffield Hallam University, United Kingdom.

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Abstract

In usability studies, when observation is made on a particular image or object on visual stimulus online, the perception of the user depends upon preceding expectations, subtle cognitive abilities and user memory. The hypothesis is usually set that subtle cognitive processes are in the form of bottom-to-up processing or a top to down processing, and this could be determined through analysis of the fixation points on the scan-path made by the eye movement on the screen. Normally, to access the variations on the scan path, user data from eye movement predictions is analysed using a four-by-four grid pattern which is superimposed on the visual stimuli to determine the user's eye fixation dispersal pattern. This is mostly based on assumption that the visual interface is viewed as a 2-dimensional visual field (Cartesian plane). As part of the contribution to usability studies, this paper approaches predictions of fixation and scan path, by determining the Euclidean distance between fixation points, and determining the shortest scan path between fixation points using the Dijkstra's Algorithm for momentous subtle cognitive response to visual stimuli in form of dynamic contents on webpages and to predict fixation points of eye movement based on constriction and dilation of the pupil response. A comparison was made between the predicted significant subtle cognitive response of the users and the trivial subtle cognitive response of the users from their fixation scan path. The trivial subtle cognitive response possesses the most high performance for all trials on eye movement data and it is set as the reliable dataset to predict eye movement on visual fields with the hypothesis that the webpage visual field is assumed to be a multi-dimensional Cartesian plane.

Keywords: Visual field, subtle cognitive response, Fixation points, Scan-path, Shortest path, Euclidean distance, Webpage visual field

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Corresponding Author:

Fatima Isiaka

Correspondent Email:

fatima.isiaka@outlook.com

1 INTRODUCTION

In the early seventy's, scan-path on the visual field was introduced by Noton and Stark [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] in their papers published as a visual research and science program which features saccadic eye movement while viewing and recognising patterns and scan-path in eye movement in pattern perception.

The researchers claimed that when a distinct visual pattern is viewed, a certain sequence of eye movement is executed and these sequences are very important in accessing the visual memory for the patterns. However, their theory is not authentic enough to form a reliable base for their result on the postulate of natural images that the human gaze selects for informative details

i.e. the fixation points tend to fall on the nearest significant details of visual stimulus like the presented image in the paper. i.e. the fixation points tend to fall on the nearest significant details of visual stimulus like the presented image in the paper. Also, this arises from the interest in scan paths as several powerful techniques have been developed that explore the statistical properties of eye movement patterns as related to important characteristics of some visual stimulus.

Some research [6, 7, 8, 9, 10] considers scan-path to be any eye-movement data collected by a gaze-tracking device, which can be archived and retrieved as recorded information about the trajectories (paths) of eyes during scanning on the visual field by viewing and analysing the visual information. Some of this information is data that consists of gaze direction, duration, and fixation position for saccade duration. Another broader definition by some work views scan-path and fixation points as sequential data that can allow application from different experiments and various submissions in a single analytical framework that deals with the visual analysis of natural and system-generated images and video sequences. These papers look at some algorithms that can predict eye movement to determine the shortest and most significant subtle cognitive perception of users on dynamic webpage stimuli. To achieve this, the pupil response (dilation and constriction) is set as a gauge for the eye movement variations and tracking of the fixations made by the subtle cognitive response of the pupil responses of the users. To understand the mechanics the proceeding section discusses the pupil response to eye movement.

2 Literature Review

Some research [11, 12, 13, 14] has found that the pupil responds to three different kinds of stimuli such as they constrict in response to brightness, constriction in response to near fixation of the pupil response, and dilatation in response to an increase in arousal, subtle cognitive and mental workload which is triggered by an external stimulus in a spontaneous event. The three pupil responses can be described by how they are related to high-level cognition to the neural pathways that control them. The functional relevance of pupil responses is how the pupil responses lead to a better view of visual stimuli and the world in general. The pupil responses serve many functions which are fully understood as one of the important functions to optimise vision for acuity and depth of field i.e. small pupils seeing sharply at a wider range of distances and also for sensitivity which is a large pupil that detects faint stimuli. The pupils change their sizes to further optimise vision for certain situations. In general, the pupil responses are identical to eye movements that include the saccadic and smooth gaze pursuit. They have properties of reflexive and voluntary action that are part of active and visual exploration.

Different forms of the algorithm [15, 16, 17, 18] have been used to compute the scan path and shortest path for eye movement and fixation predicts, one of the most basic ones is the Euclidean distances between fixation points in a Cartesian plane (Figure 1), this is the length of the line segment between the points. It is computed from the fixation points using the Pythagoras theorem (Equation 1).

$$D = \sqrt{X^2 + Y^2} \quad (1)$$

with X and Y as the two nearest points. Sometimes the Euclid distance is not represented as numbers but in degrees in the case of the multi-dimensional plane. These distances between the gaze objects that are not termed as points are usually known to be the smallest or shortest distance among the two fixation points from the two-point objects. Computational models are used to determine these short distances on the different types of dynamic contents that attract pupil responses [19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. These techniques are applied in statistical and optimisation fields for visual optimisation and predictions. For a given one-dimensional plane, the distance between the two fixation points are the real visual line is the absolute value of the numerical differences and relation of the numerical difference of the coordinates of the points on the visual field; i.e. if p and q are the two fixation points on the real line, then the computed distance between these points is given as:

$$d(p, q) = \sqrt{(p - q)^2} \quad (2)$$

For a two-dimensional Euclidean plane (Figure 1), point $p(p_1, p_2)$ and point $q(q_1, q_2)$. The distance is given as:

$$d(p, q) = \sqrt{(q_1 - p_1)^2 + (q_2 - p_2)^2} \quad (3)$$

For multi-dimensional space (Figure 2) like a webpage visual field, the different dynamic contents render the field multi-dimensional due to multiple effects like the video and image contents on the visual field. The points given by the Cartesian coordinate points in n -dimensional Euclidean space are given as the distance:

$$d(p, q) = \sqrt{(q_1 - p_1)^2 + (q_2 - p_2)^2 + \dots + \sqrt{(q_i - p_i)^2 + \dots + (q_n - p_n)^2}} \quad (4)$$

3 Method

In usability testing for visual content optimisation, different types of techniques are used for the main purpose of facilitating the task and subtle cognitive load and also to improve visual aesthetics. The method applied here is to use Dijkstra's algorithm to determine the shortest distance between fixation points and be able to predict the significant subtle cognitive response from eye movement behaviour made and webpage dynamic field on a

Figure 1: A two-dimensional Cartesian Space

Figure 2: A Multi-dimensional Cartesian Space, Courtesy: Google image

visual field. The webpage contains different contents and is assumed to be a multi-dimensional Cartesian plane that contains multiple fixation points and a scan path. The subtle cognitive response user can also be predicted from the user's pupil changes based on the dilation and constriction of the pupil sizes. The main objective is to determine the shortest possible and significant subtle cognitive perception of the users on the webpage of the visual field. The visual field is the spatial display of visual sensation that is available to the observers in psychological experiments as the entire area is seen by the eye in a fixed straight line at a point. Experimental setup on the visual field depends on the size and content of the display.

3.1 Task

Sixty participants were recruited for the first stage of the experiment, they were given a consent form to fill and a brief introduction to the given task was briefly highlighted. The main goal is to generate data on the eye movement behaviour of the participants recorded in an eye tracker (Tobii eye tracker) where they have to interact with the webpage content (Two business webpages), by simply surfing and browsing for the object of interest that either involves a high subtle cognitive load or a simple search. The process is Dijkstra's algorithm to predict the significant subtle cognitive perception of the participants from the search and compute the shortest distance between the points.

3.2 Shortest Scan-path on Visual field

To predict the shortest scan path on the visual field the problem is solved based on $f(n, \log n)$ time interval by using the recursive divide and conquer approach using the following steps.

1. Sort points on the x -Cartesian plane
2. Split the set of points to two different equally sized subsets using a vertical line $x = mid(x)$.
3. Compute the recursive problem in both sides of subsets, with a given minimum distance
4. Determine the minimum distance $min(DL)$ among pair of fixation points
5. Determine the minimum distance $min(DL), min(DR), min(DLDR)$ of the left, right and among pair of points.

To a computer, the shortest path between two fixations on a webpage visual field the data generated is set as a structured control for rudimentary optimisation. The eye movement in the visual field is considered a plane with a series of nodes connected by edges that can also be weighted edges with computed values and directional

objects. Dijkstra's algorithm is used to update the shortest path between the current node and its neighbouring nodes (Fixation points). The direction is set to the node with the lowest distance after updating the distance of all its neighbours and the process is repeated with all the subsequent neighbours until the visual field is covered. The simple process adopted Equation 5.

$$L'_{vv} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{W_{r_i} W'_{v'}}{e^{|r_{iv} - r'_{iv}|}}} \quad (5)$$

Where v and v' are the connected vertices of the fixation points served as the scan path, r_{iv} and r_{iv}' are the rating provided by the users as the user perceptions, is the weight of i^{th} user's subtle cognitive perception and wv is set as the global weight of a given recommendation for a suggested user. The result shortest distance for subtle cognitive perception is then given as L'_{vv} for all visual stimuli presented.

4 Result

The fixation points are classified based on pupil dilation and constriction, this is measured based on constriction in response to near fixation of the pupil response and also the dilating in response to an increase in arousal, a cognitive and mental workload which is triggered by webpage stimulus in a spontaneous event. Figure 3 shows an aggregate of the first webpage with fixation and scan-path with 80% accuracy to shortest path prediction to trivial fixation points. The minimum distance for the shortest path is $61.8mm$. The trivial fixation points are computed based on constriction and computed to the cognitive instance where the pupil dilates near fixation in response to mental workload.

Figure 4 shows the dilation in response to an increase in cognition or cognitive load on the webpage content. The major difference between the first and second webpage is the number of visual contents on the display field that triggers a significant cognitive perception from the user. The shortest distance is computed as $56mm$ with a 75% accuracy to trivial fixation points. The basic structure of each webpage is designed relatively similarly in terms of key elements that include links, video content, and ads. The ads can contribute to anomalies in response due to their distraction effect. The participants already have a clear and systematic approach to navigating the pages. The largest elements are the picture content and text content that users normally looked when seeing the pages for the first time.

Figure 5 shows the shortest scan path based on dilated response is $54.6mm$. The eye movement information on the page shows that the online webpage is a spatial display of random contents of informational cues and hypertext links for easy information retrieval. The perception of the informational cues is liable to the source,

Figure 3: An aggregate of the first webpage with fixation and scan-path that indicates subtle cognitive user perception

Figure 4: An aggregate of the Second webpage with fixation and scan-path that indicates trivial cognitive user perception

layout, expertise, and content on the webpages, its credibility is relevant to the types of information patches presented on the webpage. The predicted cognitive response from pupil constriction and dilation validates the eye-tracking data and the quantitative content that is analysed to understand the user's attention focus on the information patches on the diverse field.

Figure 6 displays the constriction to fixation with non or equal response in dilation to the contents on the field. The shortest minimum distance for this is 94.4mm with an 86% accuracy compared to its non-trivial fixation and scan path. The aggregate of the participants' eye distribution pattern suggests that they are more likely drawn to in the picture contents than the text contents of the webpage visual field.

5 Conclusion

This paper seeks to investigate the parallel associativity in scan-path and fixation points on usability short-term events, as part of the contribution to usability studies, the paper approaches predictions of fixation and scan-path, by determining the Euclidean distance between fixation points, predicting the shortest scan-path between fixation points using the Dijkstra's algorithm for momentous cognitive response to visual stimuli in form of dynamic contents on webpages and to predict fixation points of eye movement based on constriction and dilation of the pupil response. The comparison was done between the predicted significant cognitive response of the users and the trivial cognitive response of the users from their fixation scan path. The trivial cognitive response possesses the highest performance for all trials on eye movement data and this is set as a base for a reliable dataset to predict eye movement on visual fields with the hypothesis that the webpage visual field is assumed to be a multi-dimensional Cartesian plane. The future perspective would be to demonstrate a 3-D real-time simulation that depicts the sequential pattern of both trivial and non-trivial events of the eye movement behaviour and contributes to user-friendly analytics of scan-path and fixation predictions in usability and user experience.

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Figure 5: Second aggregate of the first webpage with fixation and scan-path that indicates trivial cognitive user perception

Figure 6: Second aggregate of the second webpage with fixation and scan-path that indicates subtle cognitive user perception

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